

Arctocephalus pusillus pusillus Cape Fur Seal

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Phylum: Chordata

Estimated genome size: 3 040 million DNA base pairs (3.04 Gigabases)

Organism size: 1.8 – 2.3 meter (length)

Distribution:

The Cape fur seal is found along the southern and southwestern coasts of Africa, ranging from Algoa Bay in the Indian Ocean (Eastern Cape, South Africa) through Namibia, up to Baia dos Tigres in southern Angola, along the Atlantic Ocean.

Importance:

The Cape fur seal is a marine apex predator that plays a critical role in maintaining a healthy marine ecosystem. It feeds on fish such as sardines and pilchards and is therefore competition with local, economically important fisheries. In Namibia, annual sealing yields meat, blubber and fur, which are then sold commercially, further contributing to the species' economic importance.

PromethION Sequencing Report: Output: 80.12 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 5.99 thousand DNA bases (kilobases)

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome length: 2.38 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.0%

[Single: 82.7%, Duplicated: 15.3%]

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